

NOTES

Effect of Heating on Some Cobalt(II) Chloride and Iodide Complexes with 4-Picoline

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Manuscript received 29 November 1982, accepted
12 September 1983

COBALT(II) complexes have been of considerable interest because of their varied structure, magnetic and electronic properties¹. The pyridine and substituted pyridine complexes of cobalt(II) have been the subject of several studies²⁻⁸. These complexes can exist in two forms, an octahedral polymeric pink form and a blue tetrahedral form.

Experimental

The complexes were prepared by adding an excess of 4-picoline to a solution of cobalt(II) halide in acetone. Pink complexes were isolated initially, which were converted to the blue form by heating at 100°.

Analyses (%), Found (Calcd.):

1. Chlorotri(4-picoline)cobalt(II)chloride, |Co(4-pic)₃Cl|Cl: C, 53.20 (52.85); H, 5.31 (5.17); N, 10.12 (10.27).
2. Iodotri(4-picoline)cobalt(II)iodide, |Co(4-pic)₃I|I: C, 37.01 (36.52); H, 3.80 (3.57); N, 7.17 (7.09).

Microanalyses were made by Mikroanalytisches Laboratorium, Bonn, Germany. The molar conductivities were obtained using a WTW, Model LBR conductometer in nitrobenzene (10⁻³ M). Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin Elmer, Model 521 as Nujol mulls and/or KBr discs. Determinations of magnetic susceptibility were made on powdered samples using Gouy method. Electronic spectra were obtained in acetone on a Cary, Model 14 M recording spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

Both the complexes are soluble in nitrobenzene and behave as uni-univalent electrolyte⁹.

The infrared spectra of 4-picoline and its complexes with transition metals have been extensively

studied. It has been shown that the ligand frequencies of the free base are shifted and split upon coordination. The assignments of the vibrational bands follow those given by Ham *et al.*¹⁰. The spectra of 4-picoline complexes are complicated and almost every band is split due to coordination. Various bands with their assignments are listed in Table I.

TABLE I—IR BANDS OF 4-PICOLINE COMPLEXES

Assignment	4-Picoline	Co(4-pic) ₃ Cl Cl	Co(4-pic) ₃ I I
8a	1603	1605 s	1610 m, 1600 m
8b	1558	1548 m	1550 vw
19a	1495	1498 m	1495 w
OH ₂ (anti def)	1441	1440 m	OB
19b	1412	1430 sh, 1420 m	OB
CH ₂ (sym def)	1370	1375 sh, 1360 w	1295 m
14	1365	1385	—
9a	1222	1230 s	1225 m
13	1209	1211 s	1203 m
18a	1070	1072-1070 m	1063 m
CH ₂ (rock)	1042	1045 sh, 1038 m	1045 vw
1	996	1019 s	1026 m
17a	972	985 w-962 sh	1010 w
5	874	880 sh	—
12	803	820 sh	805 s
10b	—	814 vs	788 s
4	728	726 s	719 m

4-pic = 4-picoline, OB = obscured, s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, vw = very weak, sh = shoulder, vs = very strong, sym = symmetric, def = deformation.

The magnetic moments corrected for ligand diamagnetism and temperature independent paramagnetism are in the range 4.52-4.66 B.M. These moments are slightly below those for |CoX₄]²⁻ species, which is what would be expected because of the higher average ligand field in the |CoL₃X|X complexes. Similar values have been observed for similar pseudotetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes¹¹.

The electronic absorption spectra of the complexes in acetone are quite similar to those of other tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes¹². These complexes can not have point group symmetry higher than C_{2v} even though their spectra might be classified as arising from T_d point group. In the 5000-30000 cm⁻¹ region, there are four major absorptions, three in the visible and one in the near infrared region.

The strong multiple absorptions between 10 and 17 kK would be assigned to ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₁ (P) (ν₃) for strictly tetrahedral symmetry. The complexes show three bands in this region which look very much like the parent |CoX₄]²⁻ ions. The multicomponent nature of the ν₃ band is because of the effects of spin orbit coupling in splitting up the ⁴T₁ (P) state and in coupling it to close lying doublet states.

The absorption in the 5-10 kK region would be assigned to ⁴A₂ → ⁴T₁ (F) (ν₂) for T_d symmetry. The

TABLE 2—MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITIES AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA

Complex	$\mu_{\text{eff}}^{\#}$	Electronic spectral peaks*						
		Ligand Field Parameters						
Complex	$\mu_{\text{eff}}^{\#}$	Observed		Calculated				
		${}^4T_1(F)$	${}^4T_1(P)$	ν_3	Dq	B'	λ'	
$[\text{Co}(4\text{-pic})_2\text{Cl}] \text{Cl}$	4.66	21.05, 19.9, 19.42 sh, 17.36(510), 16.00(930), 15.75(780), 15.15 sh, 8.00(45), 6.72(65), 6.25(39).	6.72	16.00	3.88	0.388	0.68	-0.186
$[\text{Co}(4\text{-pic})_2\text{I}] \text{I}$	4.52	22.1, 21.0, 19.60, 17.2(530), 16.08 sh, 15.25(640), 12.0(585), 8.7(35), 7.10(70), 6.0(75), 5.8(40).	6.01	15.25	3.50	0.350	0.73	-0.142

[#] In B.M., $T = 293 \pm 3^\circ$.

* The peak positions are in kK ($1\text{K} = 1\text{ cm}^{-1}$); the values in parentheses are molar absorptivity.

three bands around 6.5 kK are taken as components of ν_3 transitions of a complex of C_{2v} symmetry. Thus the electronic spectra of these complexes indicate distortion from tetrahedral symmetry. The ligand field parameters have been calculated for these complexes. The mean crystal field strength follow the sequence $\text{I} < \text{Cl}$.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported in part by the National Science Foundation, U.S.A.

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Cr(III), Mn(III) and Fe(III) Complexes of N-4-Methyl-7-Hydroxy-8-Acetocoumarinylidene-*o*-Aminophenol

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Manuscript received 5 March 1983, accepted 3 August 1983

COMPLEXES of the composition $\text{H}[\text{M}(\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_4)_2]$ [$\text{M} = \text{Cr}^{3+}$, Mn^{3+} or Fe^{3+}] with N-4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetocoumarinylidene-*o*-aminophenol (H_2MHACAP) have been prepared and characterised on the basis of elemental analysis, conductivity, electronic, infrared, pmr and magnetic measurements. Infrared spectral study reveals the tridentate (ONO) nature of the ligand. Electronic spectral data and magnetic moments of the complexes show octahedral geometry.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. Nitrates of chromium(III) and iron(III) were used. Manganese(III) acetate dihydrate was prepared by the known method¹. 4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyl coumarin was prepared² and the ligand (Schiff base), H_2MHACAP (m.p. 161°) was prepared as reported earlier^{3,4}.

For the preparation of the complexes, a slight excess of hot ethanolic solution of the ligand was added to an ethanolic solution of a metal salt dropwise with constant stirring. Sodium acetate (2 g) was added to the reaction mixture and refluxed for 30 min. The resulting mixture was concentrated to half of its original volume and the solid obtained was filtered, washed well with hot water followed by a little hot ethanol. The product was dried in air. Mn(III) complex was prepared as above without the use of sodium acetate.

Elemental analysis (Table 1), carried out by standard methods, were consistent with the formulations of the compounds. The molar conductances for $\sim 10^{-3}$ M solutions of the complexes in nitrobenzene medium range between $105\text{--}128\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mole}^{-1}$ indicating the uni-unielectrolytic nature of the compounds.

The magnetic measurements were made on a Guoy balance at room temp using $\text{Hg}[\text{CO}(\text{SCN})_4]$ as calibrant. The electronic spectra of all the complexes were recorded in DMF on a Cary-14 recording spectrophotometer. Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr in the range $4000\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ on a Perkin Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. PMR spectra in CDCl_3 were recorded on Varian T-60 instrument using TMS as internal standard.

The present Cr(III) complex exhibits the magnetic moments 3.73 B.M. which is close to spin only value for octahedral geometry^{5,6}. The spectra of Cr(III) complex exhibits bands at 11800 and 18170 and a shoulder at 23540. The ν_{O} band at 18170 and the shoulder at 23540 may be assigned to